

A crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

For caregivers of children and adolescents living with cancer

Welcome to EU4CHILD!

We are setting up focus groups with key people –like you– to understand their needs and views on the usefulness of a potential AI-based platform for Childhood Cancer. In these sessions, we aim to identify ongoing topics and potential barriers in the uptake of AI solutions for the diagnosis, prognosis, treatment and care of Childhood Cancer.

Our approach

Join us for a conversation on...

Information sources & digital skills

The patient journey in pediatric cancer

The potential of AI in pediatric cancer

The platform itself: key features & services

Meetings will be **100% online**

Sessions will be recorded

1 hour per session

This is our value proposition for you! In EU4CHILD we are focused on...

Paving the way towards personalized care

Improving quality of life & survival outcomes

Integrating patient advocacy in cancer research

Protecting & guaranteeing patients' fundamental rights

Our privacy policy

What about my data?

In compliance with the GDPR, all information you share with us shall be treated confidentially and will not be shared with any party outside of EU4CHILD's consortium. As a participant, your profile will be anonymized and no indication of your identity shall be disclosed unless with your express consent. For further details, please refer to our [Informed Consent Form](#).

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EU4CHILD receives funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783

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For survivors, children and adolescents living with cancer

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Providing reliable clinical decision support tools

Advancing cancer research & knowledge transfer

Contributing to effective multi-disciplinary work

Advocating for trust, transparency & explainability in AI

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Going beyond the standard of care in the cancer pathway

Enabling access to early diagnosis & quality treatment

Unlocking insights on AI clinical usability

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For IT experts, companies and research organizations

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Benchmarking & training explainable, robust AI models

Turning health data silos into Open Innovation

Advancing interoperability & standards in AI

Ensuring secure access & exchange of health data

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